

Women Empowerment for Accelerating the Rural Economy of Arunachal Pradesh

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“To awaken the people, it is women who must be awakened, once she is in the moves, the family moves, the villages’ moves, and nation moves”. Pt. Jawaharlal Nehru

Women empowerment is gaining popularity in the 20th century; it is era of socio- cultural reforms. Empowerment means to increase political, social, educational, and economic, Gender or spiritual strength of personal society. Women constitute the most elegant resource of society. They are regarded as the backbone in family. They play the role of mother, sister, wife, grandmother. Women are considered as the central pillar of every sphere of development in human progress. A woman is regarded as agent of for the growth and development of family as well as good society. In rural areas women are closely attached with the environment for the survival and livelihood. Protection and conservation of the forest is correlated with the role of women. In remote areas women not runs the family they also tries to earn additional wages for their family. It is very much peculiar and unique system that in Galo and some others tribes of Arunachal Pradesh women work harder than the male. They are more in cultivation than male counter parts. So if they are empowered economically, as well as socio-politically, the scenario of the rural areas will definitely transform towards the path of prosperity. For further up-liftment of the women status. International women year was declared in 1975 by United Nation. The 08th march of every year is celebrated as International women Days. The first international conference on women was held in Mexico City in1975. Followed by, Copenhagen in199 and third conference in Nairobi 1985.

The constitution of India has enshrined various specific rights which is specially related to women empowerment activities, protection, safeguard, and their all round Development. The women equality issues are address are in preamble, fundamental rights, fundamental duties & Directive principle of state policy. Like Article-14. Equality before law. Article-15, prohibition of Discrimination on ground of religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth. Article-15(d) allow to state to make special provision in favour of women and child. Article-16 equally in matters of public employment .Article-21A, free and compulsory of education to all children of the age of 6- 14 years and for girls child till 10+2 level. Article-39(d) Equal pay for work. Article-51(a), renounce practice of derogatory to the dignity of women. 73rd and 74th Amendment of the Indian constitution also provides special provision for women reservation panchayati raj institutions and urban local bodies respective national Policy for the empowerment of women also approve from 2001. The Government of India has launched various schemes and programmes to address the all round development and welfare of women and children to empower them in all spheres of their of lives. Schemes and programme like integrated child development schemes, national commission for the protection of child rights, Rajiv Gandhi schemes of empowerment adolescence (sabla). Dhan lakshami, Ujjalawala, Development of women & child in rural areas. National commission of women. Swayam Siddhi (SHG), Indira Ghandhi matriya sahyog yojana, Rashtriya Mahila kosh (National credit fund for women) for time to time. The govt. of Arunachal Pradesh has also implemented above schemes in the state for the welfare of women and children as per guidelines of the concern ministry of the Government of India. The department of social welfare, women & child development has received attention of the government of India right from first five year plan (1951-56). Empowerment of women was one the primary objectives of in ninth Plan 1997-2002. In the 10th plan (2002-2007) it was given due importance on social and economic empowerment of women and gender justice, gender budget has been also incorporate in annual budgets. Empowerment refer to provide equal opportunities , to hassle free from social caste system and traditional

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system, it also refer for economics freedom, political awareness, self reliance, self confidence to face any problem and to know about women related laws and ask to participate in national building.

In the words of A.P.J. Kalam, "Empowering women is am prerequisite for creating a good nation, when women are empowered, society with stability is assured. Empowerment of women is essential as their thought and empowered, and theirs value system leads the development of good family, good society, and ultimately a good nation". The empowerment of women is inevitable for the good family, good society and good nations. The status of women in the society can raised by empowered them economically, socially, politically, personal and to make aware of legal justice etc. The present study tries to analyze women empowerment through the role of Govt., NGOs and others civil societies in Arunachal Pradesh.

STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEMS

In modern days, there has been increase the awareness & recognition of the fact women empowerment. The women constitute to the nation building is rising. Then women empowerment will give rise to status and their dignity. Despite the various schemes and have see up and implemented for [promotion women empowerment theirs socially, politically, economically etc the desire outcome has able to achieve. still pits falls lies in this endeavors. So the research paper will try to bring out the empowerment of women through role of Govt., NGO, and Individual, etc.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Arunadati, Chattopadhyay, opines that there are various variables and attributes to measure women empowerment. His index is known as State women Index, main component are educational attainment, health status and health care facilities, demography index, economic index, political index and domestic violence index. Its can shows overall performance of states women empowerment. It also reveals their reaction that variation in the degree of social, economic, political among the India states. Rajan kumar Sahoo (2008), stated that the education is key to the development. It is effective tool for up liftment of an individual and society as a whole tribal society of Indian. How the education system can eradicate poverty and there by create awareness among women's. Education is vital weapon to reduce gender inequality in society. Dhamvamani, p (2011), reveals that the studies which were conducted virudhunagar district of Tamil Nadu in India on women up-liftment through Self Help Group. His studies tell us that SHG plays a vital role in women empowerment. His six criteria are communication skill, economics, and self-confidence, awareness against the social evils, behavioral changes, political & economic participation, and access to amenities. Kh.Thomba Singh and N. Minorca Chanu (2013), this paper reveals that how the development of micro enterprise and women entrepreneur leads to women empowerment. Empowerment of women is key element in the development of any economy. The role of enterprise is to improve the socio economic condition of the women and society. It is strengthening the women empowerment and reducing the women in equality. K. Baby (2013), in this paper she states that role of micro finance, SHG, financial intermediation, finance linkages, micro credit, micro finance can help in alleviation of poverty, empowerment of women, sustain financial outreach and impart , how the financial awareness can play pilot role in development of women to raise their status and theirs dignity etc.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the status of socio-economic status of women in Arunachal Pradesh.
2. To study the status of political participation among rural women in India.
3. To examine the behavior of individual to express women empowerment.
4. To study women contribution for sustainable development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, we took the probability of sampling as per the population where we want undertake our study. In this study each and every item as equal opportunity for being selected. The sample sizes were taken through simple random sampling technique, where selection of any individual does not influences the selection of any other.

The study has been undertaken in Gumto circle, Papumpare District, Arunachal Pradesh. It is located 30-40 km outskirts of Itanagar, Near Rono Hills. It is a newly Created circle carved out of Doimukh circle and Comprises of 10 villages namely Denka, Bogoli, Gumto-I, Gumto-II, Emchi-I Gumto-III, Emchi-II Gumto-IV, Emchi-III and Bihari Basti. According to the 2011 Census, Total Population is 1639 and total number of households is 300.out of 10 villages I took seven villages for study namely Gumto-I, Gumto-II, Emchi-I Gumto-III, Emchi-II Gumto-IV, Emchi-III. The paper was prepared from primary data through face to face survey method and from secondary sources books, research journal, research paper, published and non- published sources of Government and NGO etc. for data analysis, the percentage analysis will be used for the measurement of women empowerment.

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DISCUSSION, FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Parameter used for the measurement of women empowerment.

In this Research paper, researchers has used four types of parameters to measure women empower in the selected area of studies i.e., Gumto circle, Papumpare District, Arunachal Pradesh. As we know that there are various types of variable and attribute used by different researchers to measure women empowerment. But I have taken only four types of parameters as per my convenience and time constraints namely:-

1. Economic Empowerment.
2. Social Empowerment.
3. Political empowerment.
4. Personal empowerment.

Sample size of Population for studied Area:

Sl. no.	Name of Village	Total population as per 2011 census	No. of household	No. of household taken for study	Population of Area studied		Total population study area
					Male	female	
1	Gumto	688	118	58	173	166	339
2	Emchi	569	109	17	70	51	121

Source:- Field Study,2019.

1. Economic empowerment parameters:

Sl. No.	Measure of Economic Empowerment	Yes in (%)	NO (%)
1	Are you participating in any NGOs/ SHG etc?	25	75
2	Do You anything for your community Development	10	90
3	Do you possess risk bearing capacity?	30	70
4	Are you encouraged to take business ventures?	25	75
5	Do you have the knowledge of enterprise management?	45	55
6.	Do you use forest and natural resource in your day to day life?	90	10

Source:- Field Study, 2019.

2. Social empowerment parameters:

Sl. No.	Measure of Social Empowerment	Yes in (%)	NO (%)
1	Can you express your opinion freely in meeting / public gathering?	95	5
2	Are you able to raise voice against in justice?	80	20
3	Do you have Respect for your society?	90	10
4	Do you confidence to face any problem ?	55	45
5	Is the forest socially and culturally attached to you ?	95	5

Source:- Field Study, 2019.

3. Political empowerment parameters:

Sl. No.	Measure of political Empowerment	Yes in (%)	NO (%)
1	Do you have any knowledge about women protection laws?	25	75
2	Do you participate in election campaign?	86	24
3	Do you caste vote?	95	5
4	Do you utilize the opportunity to contest election?	69	21
5	Do you know any forest and environmental and wildlife protection laws?	35	65

Source:- Field Study, 2019.

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4. Personal empowerment parameters:

Sl. No.	Measure of personal Empowerment	Yes in (%)	NO (%)
2	Has govt. taken any step to help you?	35	65
3	Do you possess leadership quality?	45	55
4	Is there any improvement in personality development?	30	70
5	Have you attend any training program me/workshop sponsored by govt.?	25	75
6	Will you save the environment for future generation?	89	11

Source:- Field Study, 2019.

From above table we can arrive at conclusion that the women in the Gumto circle politically and social empowered but economical they still lacking behind they still depending upon their Husband. They are also very concern the protection of environment. Even though various programme and schemes has been implemented by Govt., but it is not able percolate to the grass root level. The fruit of benefit are not rest by them. There still some of pockets where these policies are not suitable to meet need of the people. For making the policies and programme effectively socio of economics condition of area must understand thoroughly. Main problems of there are

1. Lack of honest official in implementing agency of government dept.
2. Lack of awareness of among in the villages
3. Lack of education, illiteracy
4. Gender stereotyping and conservative peoples
5. Poverty, employment, and non – training program for self employment etc.
6. Poor sanitation facilities and health care
7. Poor attention of Government
8. Lack of dissemination knowledge of proper, lack of enthusiasm, honest PRI members etc.

REMEDIAL MEASURE

1. To promote awareness about the Gender education , Gender equality, laws etc
2. To organized training programme / workshop related for self / employment / avenues
3. Active and proactive involvement of education institution/ Research institution /krish vigyan Kendra, Commercial banks , NABARD and regional Rural Banks Etc
4. Tom Encourage to form NGOs/ Self Help Group.
5. Use of technology in women training programmes
6. To promote the sustainable development
7. For effectives implementation of ;laws related laws
8. To encourage for alternative source of income like Poultry, fisheries, horticulture, bee keeping , piggery etc
9. Free flow of finance transaction and financial literacy, financial inclusion etc.
10. The control in growth of population, education of women, adult education etc.

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